

**COMPARING HEALTH LITERACY LEVEL IN TURKEY
BEFORE AND AFTER THE COVID-19 PANDEMIC****Dilek Kolca¹**¹Istinye University, Vocational School of Health Services, Medical Documentation and Secretarial, Istanbul, Turkey**ABSTRACT**

Background and Objectives: *The aim of this study is health literacy before and after the COVID-19 epidemic is compared. The effect of the pandemic on health literacy is highlighted in this study.*

Materials and methods: *The study made use of the Turkish Health Literacy scale, which was created using the European Health Literacy scale's Turkish validity and reliability(1). The scale were administered to a random sample (N= 332). The scale's allowed for the calculation of the health literacy score value. The data of the study were analyzed by using T-test and one-way analysis of variance test using SPSS 25 program. Significance level was accepted as <0.05. The outcomes of data collected before and after the pandemic were compared.*

Results: *The study indicated that the health literacy score was 29.5 prior to the pandemic and 41.8 post-pandemic. The study indicated that people between the ages of 25 and 44, people with high levels of education, people who work in the health field, people who receive social security, and those whose income is higher than their outgoings all had higher average health literacy scores than the rest.*

Conclusions: *The research shows that there is a considerable impact of the pandemic on the level of health literacy when the index values before and after the pandemic are compared. The degree to which participants understand health-related information decreases as they age. Those who were health workers showed greater levels of access to health-related information, comprehension, and knowledge evaluation than did participants from other categories. Additionally, it was discovered that when participants' educational levels rise, it gets simpler to access, comprehend, and assess knowledge of health-related topics. Our study also found that as income increases, so does people's capacity to access and understand health-related information.*

Keywords: *COVID-19, Pandemic, Health Literacy*

INTRODUCTION

The world's attention was drawn to Wuhan, China's Hubei province, on December 1, 2019, when several cases of pneumonia of unknown origin were reported there. After the virus first appeared in China and quickly spread to 18 other nations, the World Health Organization (WHO) declared an emergency on January 30, 2020. Covid-19 was declared a pandemic on March 11 as it spread to 113 nations following the declaration of an emergency (2). According to data from Covid-19 show that about 80% of patients have mild illnesses, 20% need hospitalization, and about 5% need intensive care (3). Mortality rates have been noted to be higher in people over 60 and most frequently in those with hypertension, diabetes, and cardiovascular disease (4). In order to combat the virus, hygiene precautions like hand washing, wearing a mask, and keeping a physical distance have been very successful. Health literacy levels play a major role in the variation in these straightforward virus prevention methods (5).

Since the beginning of defining and assessing the functional literacy requirements of the adult population, the idea of health literacy has evolved. With these changes, it is now acknowledged that complex literacy abilities are becoming more and more necessary to participate in society. Low literacy negatively affects health and access to health care (6). Making decisions about people's health services, disease prevention, health promotion, and protection of health quality are all part of health literacy. The ability to access, comprehend, evaluate health information to make decisions about one's own health is also included (7). Terminology in health-related information causes to low health literacy, which makes it challenging to discriminate between reality and fiction. Many individuals with limited health literacy view the challenges they have in comprehending and applying knowledge of health as an impermeable barrier that existed against their will (8). Access to medical care and treatment is extremely difficult for those who do not endeavor to eliminate this barrier (9).

Health literacy is also described as the capacity of individuals to comprehend health information, make decisions, and select actions within the confines of their culture, language, and system of trust for information (10). Basic reading and writing abilities as well as the capacity to access, comprehend, review, and put into practice health facts are referred to as health literacy (11). Health literacy is typically defined as a person's ability to acquire, process, and comprehend essential health information and services required to make wise health decisions (12). In order to achieve universal health literacy, it is more reasonable to assess open communication methods between the patient and the healthcare provider (13).

Simonds (1974) was the first to suggest health literacy as a strategy that might have an impact on the health system (14). It is claimed that health literacy also has an impact on patient safety, access to healthcare, and the standard of care (15). Health literacy is crucial for accessing and using healthcare services as well as for health education and personal usage of health information. In a similarly, Van den Broucke et al. (2014) pointed out that in order to promote health-related be-

haviors, educational interventions related to health literacy should be developed (16). Increased community health education can boost health literacy, according to a Japanese study (17). Participants with higher levels of health literacy were found to be more likely to get physicals or cancer screenings. Low cancer screening rates have been linked to low health literacy, according to numerous studies (18;19). Studies have also demonstrated that patients who have higher levels of health literacy use medical services more effectively (20).

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The study was inspired by a PhD thesis. This study was designed to examine the differences in health literacy between Turkey's pre-pandemic era and the COVID-19 process. Data were gathered for the study using a quantitative research methodology, with the comparison model serving as the foundation. The study was conducted in the province of Istanbul, which has the most COVID-19 cases per capita in Turkey. Participation in the study was open to everyone.

The study used the Turkish Health Literacy Scale, whose reliability and validity were examined by Okyay and Abacigil (2016) prior to the pandemic (1). The degree of health literacy among participants with COVID-19 has been identified. Health literacy scale consists of 2 sub-dimensions; 'treatment and service', 'prevention of diseases/health promotion'. It has 4 processes, each of which defines 2 sub-dimensions: accessing, comprehending, evaluating, and using health-related knowledge. This scale has 32 items related to health literacy, scored on a 5-point Likert scale (strongly agree, agree, have no opinion, disagree, strongly disagree). The scale's allowed for the calculation of the health literacy score value. The data of the study were analyzed by using T-test and one-way analysis of variance test using SPSS 25 program. Significance level was accepted as <0.05. The Cronbach Alpha coefficient was 0.927 in Okyay and Abacigil's (2016) study and 0.779 in our study. The scale's reliability that is more than 0.60 is acceptable.

The study's objective is to identify participants who have gone through the Covid-19 process. Therefore, the research's participation was chosen using a simple random sampling method. A total of 332 voluntarily participating individuals were chosen at random, and their health literacy levels were assessed. It was determined whether the study's sample size was adequate using the Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) test. The test's findings revealed that the sample size was adequate. The participant's health literacy results were compared to those from the pre-pandemic health literacy study.

RESULTS

The Findings Regarding Descriptive Characteristics of the Participants:

The majority of the study's participants 53% are aged 25 to 34; men make up 29.8% of the participants while women make up 70.2%. 69% of participants are single, 31% are married, and 33.1% have graduated from high school or an undergraduate program. It was shown that 44.6%

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7676579

of the participants had less income than expenses, 51.5% did not have social security, and 41.9% of participants consists of the majority as students.

Analysis of Health Literacy Scale Factors

It was determined using the Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) test whether the sample size was appropriate for factor analysis. KMO value is 0.921. It is clear that the sample size is adequate for the data because the statistic is bigger than 0.50 (21). The sample size was determined to be "sufficient" for the factor analysis.

Table 1. Results of the Health Literacy Scale's Explanatory Factor Analysis

Factors	Eigen Value	ExplainedVariance %	CumulativeVariance %	Cronbach Alpha Coefficient
1	10.78	33.70	33.7	0.779
2	2.03	6.34	40.0	
3	1.49	4.65	44.7	
4	1.36	4.27	48.9	
5	1.27	3.98	52.9	

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Sample Adequacy: 0.921

the Bartlett's Sphericity Test's Chi-Square Value: 4711,434 Sd= 6 p=0.000

Table 1 factor loads analysis reveals that all items have factor loads greater than 0.30.

Comparison of Health Literacy Distribution

The participants in this study were found to have sufficient health literacy, with a score of 41.8, as opposed to Okyay and Abacıgil's (2016) finding that Turkey's health literacy index average was 29.5 at a low health literacy level. According to the participants in the study by Okyay and Abacıgil (2016), 5.8% had good health literacy, 24.8% had adequate health literacy, 42.2% had restricted health literacy, and 27.2% had insufficient health literacy. 52% of the participants in this study had great health literacy, 43% had good health literacy, and 5% had inadequate health literacy, it was discovered.

Analysis of Quantitative Findings Related to Participants' HL Level:

There is no significant difference gender and marital status between the health literacy sub-dimensions ($p>0.05$). According to the participants' health insurance, there is a significant difference between the groups in the ANOVA test results between the levels of health literacy ($p<0.05$). Understand information relevant to health regarding social security is significantly different statistically in table 2 ($p<0.05$). The post-hoc Scheffe test was used to determine the cause of the difference. In terms of understand information relevant to health, there is a differ-

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7676579

ence between the average of participants with social security ($X=4.13$) and the average of individuals without social security ($X=3.93$).

Table 2. Comparison of the HL Scale and Sub-Dimensions of the Gender, Marital Status and Health Insurance

	Factors	Variable	N	X	SS	P
Gender	Health information access	Male	99	4.16	0.74	.268
		Female	233	4.25	0.69	
	Understanding health information	Male	99	4.03	0.79	.998
		Female	233	4.03	0.81	
	Evaluate health information	Male	99	4.08	0.58	.836
		Female	233	4.07	0.60	
	Access to disease prevention information	Male	99	4.13	0.68	.915
		Female	233	4.13	0.67	
	Evaluating disease prevention information	Male	99	3.85	0.74	.120
		Female	233	3.71	0.71	
Marital Status	Health information access	Married	103	4.22	0.70	.992
		Single	229	4.22	0.71	
	Understanding health information	Married	103	4.08	0.81	.470
		Single	229	4.01	0.80	
	Evaluate health information	Married	103	4.00	0.62	.157
		Single	229	4.10	0.58	
	Access to disease prevention information	Married	103	4.03	0.72	.070
		Single	229	4.18	0.65	
	Evaluating disease prevention information	Married	103	3.72	0.68	.549
		Single	229	3.77	0.74	
	Health information access	No	161	4.23	0.68	.841
		Yes	171	4.22	0.72	
	Understanding health information	No	161	3.93	0.83	.021*
		Yes	171	4.13	0.76	

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7676579

Health Insurance	Evaluate health information	No	161	4.07	0.59	.933
		Yes	171	4.07	0.59	
	Access to disease prevention information	No	161	4.09	0.76	.273
		Yes	171	4.17	0.59	
	Evaluating disease prevention information	No	161	3.75	0.73	.910
		Yes	171	3.76	0.71	

* Significant at the $p < 0.05$ level

Only knowing the information about understand information relevant to health and the participants' ages were significantly different ($p < 0.05$) when the sub-dimensions of health literacy were compared to their ages in Table 3. We looked at the post-hoc Scheffe test scores to determine which groups had different knowledge of treatment and services. The mean of the age groups 25–34 and 35–44 ($X=4.17$) and the group of people aged 45 and older ($X=3.58$) were found to differ in comprehension the health-related knowledge.

The educational status of the participants and the factors of understand health information, appraising health information, and access information relevant to disease prevention are statistically different ($p < 0.05$). It was determined which groups the difference stemmed from using the post-hoc Scheffe test. The difference between the means of primary school graduates ($X=3.50$), high school graduates ($X=3.95$), and postgraduate graduates ($X=4.46$) was revealed in terms of understand information relevant to health. The difference between undergraduate graduates ($X=4.00$) and graduate graduates ($X=4.36$) in the sub-factor of appraise information relevant to health. The averages of primary school pupils ($X=3.62$) and graduate students ($X=4.43$) differ in terms of access information relevant to disease prevention sub-factor.

Table 3. Comparison of the HL Scale and Sub-Dimensions of the Age, Educational and Occupation Status

	Factors	Variable	N	X	SS	P
Age	Health information access	15-24	177	4.24	0.70	.673
		25-34	94	4.25	0.72	
		35-44	43	4.19	0.64	
		45 over	18	4.04	0.82	
	Understanding health information	15-24	177	3.97	0.80	.012*
		25-34	94	4.17	0.76	
		35-44	43	4.17	0.71	

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7676579

		45 over	18	3.58	1.07	
	Evaluate health information	15-24	177	4.08	0.56	.614
		25-34	94	4.09	0.67	
		35-44	43	4.07	0.54	
		45 over	18	3.89	0.64	
	Access to disease prevention information	15-24	177	4.13	0.71	.736
		25-34	94	4.17	0.65	
		35-44	43	4.11	0.60	
		45 over	18	3.98	0.67	
	Evaluating disease prevention information	15-24	177	3.78	0.69	.303
		25-34	94	3.69	0.73	
		35-44	43	3.85	0.74	
		45 over	18	3.53	0.69	
Educational Status	Health information access	Primary School	10	3.93	0.87	.186
		High School	110	4.22	0.65	
		Associate Degree	76	4.28	0.74	
		Bachelor's Degree	104	4.15	0.73	
		Postgraduate	26	4.50	0.57	
		PhD	6	4.17	0.86	
	Understanding health information	Primary School	10	3.50	1.25	.008*
		High School	110	3.95	0.73	
		Associate Degree	76	3.99	0.89	
		Bachelor's Degree	104	4.06	0.75	
		Postgraduate	26	4.46	0.69	
		PhD	6	4.50	0.55	
	Evaluate health information	Primary School	10	3.82	0.82	.029*
		High School	110	4.03	0.55	
		Associate Degree	76	4.13	0.59	
		Bachelor's Degree	104	4.00	0.60	

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7676579

		Postgraduate	26	4.36	0.55	
		PhD	6	4.37	0.39	
	Access to disease prevention information	Primary School	10	3.62	1.23	.020*
		High School	110	4.08	0.73	
		Associate Degree	76	4.21	0.61	
		Bachelor's Degree	104	4.09	0.59	
		Postgraduate	26	4.43	0.56	
		PhD	6	4.33	0.45	
	Evaluating disease prevention information	Primary School	10	3.45	0.91	.105
		High School	110	3.79	0.69	
		Associate Degree	76	3.77	0.80	
		Bachelor's Degree	104	3.64	0.65	
		Postgraduate	26	4.02	0.71	
		PhD	6	4.04	0.87	
Occupation	Health information access	Worker	30	3.23	0.70	.070
		Civil Servant/Retired	58	4.01	0.83	
		Student	139	4.25	0.67	
		Health Manager	13	4.36	0.63	
		Academician	11	4.45	0.43	
		Doctor	5	3.93	0.68	
		Nurse/Midwife	27	4.09	0.84	
		Health Technician	49	4.41	0.55	
	Understanding health information	Worker	30	3.77	0.91	.008*
		Civil Servant/Retired	58	4.05	0.81	
		Student	139	3.92	0.85	
		Health Manager	13	4.46	0.48	
		Academician	11	4.23	1.03	
		Doctor	5	4.90	0.22	
Nurse/Midwife		27	4.09	0.52		

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7676579

		Health Technician	49	4.20	0.63	
	Evaluate health information	Worker	30	3.87	0.65	.055
		Civil Servant/Retired	58	3.93	0.66	
		Student	139	4.09	0.58	
		Health Manager	13	4.15	0.54	
		Academician	11	4.33	0.54	
		Doctor	5	4.64	0.54	
		Nurse/Midwife	27	4.13	0.52	
		Health Technician	49	4.13	0.52	
	Access to disease prevention information	Worker	30	3.79	0.94	.010*
		Civil Servant/Retired	58	4.07	0.56	
		Student	139	4.15	0.71	
		Health Manager	13	4.14	0.75	
		Academician	11	4.29	0.46	
		Doctor	5	4.96	0.09	
		Nurse/Midwife	27	4.08	0.59	
		Health Technician	49	4.26	0.49	
	Evaluating disease prevention information	Worker	30	3.37	0.86	.027*
		Civil Servant/Retired	58	3.76	0.72	
		Student	139	3.79	0.70	
		Health Manager	13	3.77	0.73	
		Academician	11	4.07	0.54	
		Doctor	5	4.40	0.45	
		Nurse/Midwife	27	3.66	0.77	
		Health Technician	49	3.75	0.64	
Income-expenditure	Health information access	Income less than expenses	148	4.14	0.76	.050*
		Income equals expense	139	4.33	0.60	
		Income more than expenses	45	4.19	0.75	
	Understanding health	Income less than expenses	148	3.90	0.83	

information	Income equals expense	139	4.14	0.72	.032*
	Income more than expenses	45	4.11	0.91	
Evaluate health information	Income less than expenses	148	4.00	0.58	.129
	Income equals expense	139	4.14	0.62	
	Income more than expenses	45	4.10	0.52	
Access to disease prevention information	Income less than expenses	148	4.07	0.73	.265
	Income equals expense	139	4.16	0.65	
	Income more than expenses	45	4.24	0.57	
Evaluating disease prevention information	Income less than expenses	148	3.70	0.74	.476
	Income equals expense	139	3.79	0.72	
	Income more than expenses	45	3.79	0.65	

* Significant at the $p < 0.05$ level

The occupational categories of the participants and the sub-factors of understanding information important to health, accessing information relevant to disease prevention, and disease prevention are statistically different, as shown in ($p < 0.05$). The difference's cause was determined using a post-hoc Scheffe test. The test revealed a significant difference in the means for understanding health-related information and accessing information related to disease prevention between the working group ($X=3.77$) and doctors ($X=4.90$). Additionally, compared to doctors ($X=4.96$), the average access information relevant to disease prevention is lower for employees ($X=3.79$). Employees appraise information relevant to disease prevention is on average lower ($X=3.79$) than doctors' ($X=4.96$).

A statistically significant difference between the sub-factors of access information relevant to health and income-expenditure evaluation and understand information relevant to health was identified ($p < 0.05$). The post-hoc Scheffe test was used to determine the cause of the difference. The test results show that the averages of those whose income is less than their expenditure ($X=4.14$) and those whose income is equal to their expenditure ($X=4.33$) differ from one another in terms of their Access information relevant to health. It can be shown that the averages of participants whose income is less than their expenses ($X=3.90$) and those whose income is equal to their expenses ($X=4.14$) differ from one another in how they perceive their understand information relevant to health.

DISCUSSION

Within the context of the COVID-19 pandemic outbreak and in comparison, to pre-pandemic levels, health literacy was assessed in this study. Turkey's level of health literacy was evaluated

using the "Turkey Health Literacy Scale-32 (TSOY-32)" developed by Abacgil and Okyay (2016) with cooperation from the General Directorate of Health Promotion of the Ministry of Health. We conducted this study following the pandemic, and the results showed that 52% of participants had excellent health literacy, 43% had good health literacy, and 5% had low health literacy. Although Okyay and Abacgil's (2016) study reported that the overall health literacy score was 29.5 before the pandemic, the sample in the study was determined to have a sufficient level of health literacy, with a total health literacy index value of 41.8. It is clear from comparing the two figures that the epidemic has a positive effect on health literacy. The participants' health literacy was distributed as follows: 42.2% problematic, 27.8% inadequate, 24.8% adequate, and 5.8% excellent before the pandemic. Following the pandemic, our study found that 52% of participants had excellent health literacy, 43% had adequate health literacy, and 5% had limited health literacy.

When demographic data and health literacy are compared, contrary to the findings of earlier researchers, there is no evidence of a relationship between gender or marital status and health literacy. However, there was a difference in health literacy levels when age, education, occupation, social security, income, and expenditure were compared. According to Yakar et al. (2019), people with poor vision, married people, people with children, and women with less education than a high school certificate all had lower health literacy levels than the other groups (22). In another study, the Turkish health literacy scale was used, and the individuals who had completed high school or higher education, those who had received prior health education, and men all shown higher health literacy than the other participants. Low education levels are associated with lower levels of health literacy than secondary or higher education levels (24). Participants who are older have less health literacy than patients who are younger (23). Men's health literacy is also substantially lower than women's, and single people's health literacy is significantly lower than that of married individuals. In the study by Do et al. (2020), it was discovered that individuals with high health literacy adhered to infection prevention and control methods better, adopted healthier lifestyles, and were more adept at identifying COVID-19 symptoms (25).

Conclusion: This study reveals pre- and post-pandemic health literacy. The originality of the research is boosted by the lack of studies contrasting health literacy in Turkey before and after the Covid-19 pandemic. The study's most striking finding was that the pandemic had a favorable impact on health literacy. Health literacy has been found to be positively influenced by higher education levels, youth, health professions, social security, and high income. The majority of the sample population is young and female, which is the study's biggest flaw. No statistical difference in the tests was produced by this circumstance. It is advised that future studies in this field take the distribution between groups into account. Additionally, it is believed that the pandemic did not purposefully increase health literacy. In order to improve health literacy in daily life, society's participation should be increased on the basis of voluntarism and awareness-raising. A rise in health literacy will be ensured as a result, aiding in the advancement of public health.

Declarations of interest: No conflict of interest has been declared by the authors

Author Contributions: D.K. (First author), Introduction author/Original researcher (50%); A.Ö. (Second Author), Methodologist/ Assistant Researcher (30%); G.K. (Third Author), Methodologist/Assistant Researcher (20%)

Abbreviations: HL: Health Literacy, PhD: Doctorate

REFERENCES

1. Abacıgil, F. & Okyay, P. Turkish adaptation of the European Health Literacy Scale. Okyay, P. & Abacıgil, F. (Ed.) Turkish Health Literacy Scales in the reliability and validity study (p. 21-41). Ankara: T.C. Ministry of Health Publication No: 1025, 2016.
2. Khanna, R. C., Cicinelli, M. V., Gilbert, S. S., Honavar, S. G., & Murthy, G. V. COVID-19 pandemic: Lessons learned and future directions. *Indian journal of ophthalmology*, 2020; 68(5), 703-710.
3. Team, E. The epidemiological characteristics of an outbreak of 2019 novel coronavirus diseases (COVID-19)—China, 2020. *China CDC weekly*, 2020; 2(8), 113.
4. Çevik, M., Bamford, CGG ve Ho, A. COVID-19 pandemisi—klinikyenler için odaklanmış bir inceleme. *Klinik Mikrobiyoloji ve Enfeksiyon*, 2020; 26 (7), 842-847.
5. Khoo, E. J., & Lantos, J. D.. Lessons learned from the COVID-19 pandemic. *Acta Paediatrica* (Oslo, Norway: 1992), 2020; 109(7), 1323.
6. Berkman, N. D., Davis, T. C., McCormack, L. (2010). Health Literacy: What Is It?, *Journal of Health Communication*, 15(2), 9-19. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10810730.2010.499985>
7. Kickbusch, I. Pelikan, R. M., Apfel, F., Tsouros, A. D. (Ed.). *Health literacy The solid facts*, Denmark: WHO Regional Office for Europe, 2013.
8. Sezgin, D. Understanding Health Literacy, *Galatasaray University Journal of Communication*, 2013; 3, 73-92.
9. Freedman, D. A., Bess, K. D. Tucker, H. A. Boyd, D. L., Tuchman, A. M., Wallston, K. A. Public Health Literacy Defined, *American Journal of Preventive Medicine*, 2009; 36(5), 446-451. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.amepre.2009.02.001>
10. Hepburn, M. Health Literacy, Conceptual Analysis for Disease Prevention, *International Journal of Collaborative Research on Internal Medicine & Public Health*, 2012; 4(3), 227-238.
11. Xu, C., Zhang, X. ve Wang, Y. Mapping of health literacy and social panic via web search data during the COVID-19 public health emergency: infodemiological study. *Journal of Medical Internet Research*, 2020; 22(7), 1-8.

12. Rademakers, J., Waverijn, G., Rijken, M., Osborne, R., ve Heijmans, M. Towards a comprehensive, person-centred assessment of health literacy: translation, cultural adaptation and psychometric test of the Dutch Health Literacy Questionnaire. *BMC Public Health*, 2020; 20(1), 1-12. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12889-020-09963-0>
13. Weiss, B. D. Health literacy, *The Arizona University Elder Care A Resource for Interprofessional Providers*, 2003; 1-2.
14. Simonds, S. K. Health education as social policy. *Health Education Monograph*, 1974; 2, 1-25.
15. Hersh, L., Salzman, B., Snyderman, D. Health Literacy in Primary Care Practice, *American Family Physician*, 2015; 92(2), 118-124.
16. Van den Broucke, S. et al. Enhancing the effectiveness of diabetes self-management education: the diabetes literacy Project, *Horm. Metab. Res.*, 2014; 46 (13), 933-938.
17. Ishikawa, H. et al. Developing a measure of communicative and critical health literacy: a pilot study of Japanese office workers, *Health Promot. Int.*, 2008, 23 (3), 269-274.
18. Kim, K. Han, H.R. Potential links between health literacy and cervical cancer screening behaviors: a systematic review *Psychooncology*, 2016; 25 (2), 122-130.
19. Oldach, B.R., Katz, M.L. Health literacy and cancer screening: a systematic review *Patient Educ. Couns.*, 2014; 94 (2), 149-157.
20. Goto, E., Ishikawa, H., Okuhara, T., & Kiuchi, T. Relationship of health literacy with utilization of health-care services in a general Japanese population. *Preventive medicine reports*, 2019; 14, 100811.
21. Raynor, D. K. T. Health literacy. *BMJ*, 2012; 344(2), 1-2. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmj.e2188>
22. Akbulut, Ö.&Çapık, C. Sample Size for Multivariate Statistical Analysis, *Journal of Nursing*, 2022; 25(2), 111-116.
23. Yakar, B., Gömleksiz, M. ve Prinççi, E. Health Literacy Levels of Patients Applying to a University Hospital Outpatient Clinic and Affecting Factors, *Euras J Fam Med*, 2019; 8(1):27-35.
24. Rademakers, J., Waverijn, G., Rijken, M., Osborne, R., ve Heijmans, M. (2020). Towards a comprehensive, person-centred assessment of health literacy: translation, cultural adaptation and psychometric test of the Dutch Health Literacy Questionnaire. *BMC Public Health*, 20(1), 1-12. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12889-020-09963-0>
25. Do B, Tran T, Phan D, Nguyen H, Nguyen T, Nguyen H, Ha T, Dao H, Trinh M, ... Health Literacy, eHealth Literacy, Adherence to Infection Prevention and Control Procedures, Lifestyle Changes, and Suspected COVID-19 Symptoms Among Health Care Workers During Lockdown: Online Survey, *Journal of Medical Internet Research*, 2020; 22(11), 1-18. doi: <https://doi.org/10.2196/22894>